

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FOUNDATIONS OF TRANSLATOR TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This article is about psycholinguistic foundations of translator training in our country and the requirements for them.

This articles thesis is dedicated to one of the urgent tasks in the system of higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the importance of the components of the role of the educational system in psycholinguistic foundations of translator training and its features. Analysis of the existing system of translator/interpreter education, analysis and evaluation of students' psychological competence, use of theoretical study of the problem, analysis of current translator/interpreter education system, and use of surveys, unique written assignments (essays, projects), practical assessments, and multiple-choice exams at the midterm and final exams. The research involved 50 students from the first to the fourth year of the "Translation studies" program. Thus, we used questionnaires to ascertain the students' general knowledge of psychology of translation, written assignments (essays, projects), personal attitudes and ideas toward psychological training, and oral tests to ascertain the students' specialized knowledge and abilities in the field of psychology of translation and communication after some instruction. There are no specific courses designed to fill a gap, according to a thorough review of the current translator/interpreter curricula and syllabi of academic disciplines offered as required and optional courses in Uzbekistan and foreign universities.

In order to increase students' psychological knowledge and, more crucially, to cultivate their psychological abilities and practices State Educational Standards have been adopted five times at various times since the beginning of translation studies in the system of higher education (1996): in 1996, 2001, 2004, 2006, and 2012. However, a field called "Psychology and Pedagogy" that addressed the issues of general professional understanding of psychology and communication was only introduced in the State Educational Standard of the 2001 academic year.

We can distinguish two approaches in terms of psychological approaches to translation and interpretation: 1) Psychology of translation, which focuses on the investigation of the precise psychological mechanisms of perception, interpretation, memory, imagination, and message reformulation, and 2) Psychology of communication, psychology of interaction between the client and the interpreter or translator. Thus, the debate over whether the cognitive or communicative functions of translation should take precedence was centered on these two orientations.

A distinct framework that includes the elements of inspiring, inciting, orienting, knowing, and acting is another characteristic of translation. As a result, just like other speech activities like speaking, listening, reading, and writing, it is dependent on the process through which language, or speech, shapes and formulates mind.

Additionally, thinking reformulation is implied by translation. Reformulation is a crucial component of the internal workings of translation and is distinguished by many varying degrees of consciousness and, more significantly, taking place at various stages or intervals of the process

As communication is a key component of any translator's or interpreter's multifaceted professional activity, we believe that teaching future specialists to translate and interpret as communicative activities is the correct approach. Because of this, the psychology of communication should be taught using the special psychological mechanisms of translation, understanding, memory, imagination, operation of reformulating.

The science of psychology offers a rational method for comprehending the work of an interpreter or translator who frequently interacts with persons of various social statuses, psychological kinds, cultural affiliations, and professional specialties.

Therefore, based on the research above, we draw the conclusion that the psychology course for aspiring translators and interpreters should be structured as teaching for communication for the following reasons: In order to effectively master translation as a communicative activity, translators must develop the following psycho-physiological skills: intelligence, memory, learning styles, input, imagination, processing, response, and ethics. A higher level of mastery of translation as a communicative activity enables the future translators/interpreters to provide an adequate perception, interaction, and influence on the target audience.

It is carried out in parallel with the above-mentioned operations. In this regard, the time factor is a determining feature of translation activity in simultaneous implementation. One of the psychological characteristics of a synchronous translator is the essential parameters of the professional reliability of a translator-synchronous translator.

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